

THE ART OF TALMEH IN THE POETRY OF ERKIN VAKHIDOV

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Abstract: the article examines the role of poetic art in poetics and its poetic functions in poetry. In this regard, the internal aspects of the art of talme in the poems of Erkin Vakhidov are analyzed.

Key words: poetry, talme art, names of historical figures, names of famous works, heroes of works, names of celestial bodies.

Annotatsiya: maqolada shariyatda badiiy sanatlarning tutgan orni va uni sherdagi poetik vazifalari haqida fikr yuritilgan. Shu jihatdan Erkin Vohidov sherlaridagi talme sanati ichiki korinishlari tahlil etilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: shariyat, talme sanati, tarixiy shaxslar nomi, mashhur asar nomlari, asar qahramonlari, osmon jismlari nomi.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль поэтического искусства в поэтике и его поэтические функции в стихах. В этом плане анализируются внутренние аспекты искусства тальмех в стихах Эркина Вахидова.

Ключевые слова: поэзия, искусство тальме, имена исторических деятелей, названия известных произведений, герои произведений, названия небесных тел

Each poetic art used in the poem determines the skill of the creator. In particular, the art of talme requires strong historical knowledge from the poet. In turn, by using the art of talme in poetry, the creator pursues several goals:

1. In order to further clarify the idea of the poem, compare it with historical events (figures), differentiate and compare it to that event;

2. To encourage the reader to think in depth by referring to a certain work, hero, event in the poem (of course, in order to understand the idea of the poem more deeply one should be aware of the meaning of that work or the fate of the hero.);

3. To allow the reader to enjoy both the historical truth and the artistic appeal of the poem at the same time.

Of course, in order to achieve these goals, the poet must be aware of classical literature, the reality of the past, and at the same time, be familiar with the ancient values and folklore of his people.

Bright examples of Talmeh art can be seen in the work of Erkin Vahidov. The work of Erkin Vahidov, the favorite artist of the Uzbek people, one of the brightest manifestations of our poetry, is extremely meaningful and unique. This is reflected in the tradition and innovation of the poet's use of artistic arts. In particular, the art of talmeh was used extremely widely. Examples of the art of talmeh in the poet's poems can be divided into the following types in terms of meaning:

1. Creating the art of talmeh by mentioning the names of historical figures.

Chulg'anib sokin xayolga

Jim yotar sog'onalar.

Ne ko'rar **Mirzo Ulug'bek**

Besh asrlik xobida?

Bosh egib ustoz **Ulug'bek**

Qoshida turdim bu tong,

Charx urib ko'nglim xayolning

Otashin girdobida [1, 67].

In his poem named "Samarkand", the poet mentions the history and ancient monuments of Samarkand, and talks about the grave of our great grandfathers, especially Mirzo Ulugbek. Saying "Ilk muallimdir Samarqand ilmi aflok bobida", he emphasizes the great contribution of Ulugbek in the field of astronomy.

Navoiy sham kabi yonib,
Xazondek sarg'ayib so'lmish,
Varaqalar ham olibdur
Sohibi devoni rangidan.

Fuzuliy Karbalo dashtin
Quyundek kezdi **Qays** birlan,
Dili hech topmadi taskin
Davarning boda, bangidan [1, 91].

This excerpt is taken from the poem named "Treasure" by Erkin Vahidov. By calling the poem a treasure, he refers to our great ancestors, who devoted their life to the development of Turkish literature and to spread its popularity throughout the world.

2. Creating the art of talmeh by mentioning the names of famous works.

Yosh Verterni o'qib bir kun meni ham-
Sevarmikin kimdir, deya o'ylading
G'oyibona yo'llaringga intizor,
Allakimning kutishini bilmaysan [1, 12]

This poem refers to the work of the great German poet Johann Wolfgang Goethe called "The Sorrows of Young Werther". The poet encourage the girl to think about love, which she has not met, bringing "The Sorrows of Young Werther" to the hands of the girl. In the poem, the thoughts of a girl who hopes to meet her true love, like the characters of the work, and the appeal of the lyrical hero to her are sung.

3. Create the art of talmeh by mentioning the names of characters of the play

Sevgi sahsosida qolmish
Necha **Majnundan** g'ubor,
Necha **Farhod** gardi yotgan
Bistunning tog'ida [1, 62].

Majnun is a common image of a lover in Eastern literature. Farhad is the image of a perfect person who has reached the peak of love. Naturally, every poet, especially

Erkin Vahidov, wrote passionate poems about love. The images of Laili, Majnun, Farhad, and Shirin are often found in these poems. The most interesting thing is that the poet always discovered new meanings from these names. At the same time, he kept traditionalism: he depicted the heroes of the epic as symbols of love.

4. Creating the art of talmeh by mentioning the names of celestial bodies.

Ana **Hulkar** – yeti qiz imlar meni yiroqdan,

Oydin ko'chalar bo'y lab shu'lalarda oqurman.

Ulug'bek qadam qo'ygan bu muqaddas tuproqdan

Ulug'bek nigoh tikkan yulduzlarga boqurman [1, 23]

O'zingsanku mening yulduzim,

Surayyodan, Zuhrodan ortiq.

Ko'k toqidan olmadek uzib,

Birin senga qilaymi tortiq? [1, 26]

In this verse, the lyrical hero compares his sweetheart to Surayya and Venus. It is known to all of us that there is a tradition of comparing sweethearts to the moon and the stars in classical literature.

Rost g'azal avjida barcha

Oy ila **Zuhro** emas,

Ko'p erur somonchilar ham

She'riyat osmonida □ [61]

"Moon and Zuhro in the lines taken from Yoshlik Divan are referring to the mature figures of ghazal writers in our literature. As is the case everywhere, there are no poets who are untalented in their field, and who have finished ghazals. No. He compares them to strawmen, because in science, strawmen are not a kind of star, but a dim light that surrounds the sky.

Erkin Vahidov's poetry contains various manifestations of artistic arts, which indicate that there are many aspects of the poet's poems that have not yet been explored. In addition, it can be seen that the art of talmeh in the work of the poet was a unique

artistic tool for strengthening the poetic content and reviving the fragments of history. In addition, these talmehs are essentially diverse.

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